

1 **Fetal heart rate and nuchal translucency as first**
2 **trimester markers of preterm birth.**

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34 **ABSTRACT**

35 Objective

36 To evaluate whether first trimester fetal heart rate (FHR) and nuchal
37 translucency (NT) associate with preterm birth (PTB).

38 Methods

39 This was a comparative case-control study of 518 normal pregnancies with no
40 history of PTB of which 272 delivered at term (TB) and 246 progressed to
41 spontaneous PTB prior to 37, 34, 32 and 28 weeks. Fetal heart rate (FHR)
42 and nuchal translucency (NT) values at the first trimester scan were
43 compared by means of univariable (Mann-Whitney) and multivariable logistic
44 regression analysis considering hourglass membranes (HM) as the most
45 severe PTB subgroup. Finally severity trends for both parameters were
46 investigated using correlations with gestational age (GA) at delivery and
47 Kruskal-Wallis tests.

48 Results

49 Regardless of GA at delivery, pregnancies affected with PTB showed higher
50 FHR and thicker NT at the first trimester scan. The association was confirmed
51 by the multivariable analysis and the severity trends, which paired the highest
52 FHR and NT values with the most severe cases of PTB ($p < 0.001$) ($p < 0.0001$).

53 Conclusion

54 Fetuses with subsequent late, early and very early PTB show higher values of
55 NT and FHR at the first trimester scan.

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57 **KEY WORDS**

58 Preterm birth, fetal heart rate, first trimester screening, nuchal translucency.

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68 **INTRODUCTION**

69 Preterm birth (PTB) occurs in 10% of the world pregnancies [1,2]. However its
70 incidence varies according to the wealth and socioeconomic situation of the
71 different countries: in the underdeveloped world, including India and most
72 African countries, it approaches 20%, while in Europe and North America its
73 incidence is closer to 5 % [1,2], a figure that has been increased after the
74 advent of assisted reproduction and its repercussion on the number of
75 multiple pregnancies [3,4]. Unfortunately, although management of PTB has
76 notably improved with the use of lung maturation and utero-inhibitory drugs, it
77 still present dreadful lifelong consequences derived from neurological
78 complications of prematurity [5].

79 Most of PTB is of unknown origin. However, the hypothesis of inflammation
80 [6-8] as a key mechanism triggering contractions and cervix effacement,
81 which also occurs in term labor [9,10] has gained increasing importance.
82 Moreover, treatment with antibiotics has proven to be useful at early stages,
83 eradicating a proportion of cases with PTB, intact membranes, and intra-
84 amniotic inflammation [11].

85 Interestingly, diabetes [12-14] and dental infections [15-17] may also lead to
86 PTB, probably through a similar activation of the inflammatory cascade that
87 could theoretically modify diverse biological parameters such as fetal heart
88 rate (FHR) and heart performance [18-23]. In fact, higher FHR values in the
89 first trimester were observed in association with type I diabetes [24]. In his
90 regard, we hypothesized whether the FHR increase could be caused by
91 maternal inflammation due to chronic diabetes and whether the scenario
92 leading to the FHR increase could be resembled in case of inflammation
93 causing preterm birth. In this work we aimed to evaluate first trimester FHR as
94 a possible marker for PTB along with nuchal translucency, a well-known first
95 trimester marker of adverse pregnancy outcome, also related with PTB [25].

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102 **MATERIAL AND METHODS**

103 This was a comparison study of two groups of normal pregnancies (N=518)
104 with no history of PTB of which, 272 were delivered at term, 37 weeks or
105 more, (TB) and 246 progressed to spontaneous PTB. In both groups, data
106 from the first trimester scan were collected, including FHR, nuchal
107 translucency (NT), gestational age (GA) at examination, maternal age, weight
108 and height, parity, number of gestations, smoking and type of conception
109 (spontaneous or assisted reproduction). Finally, data related with birth were
110 also documented, including the type of event leading to labor onset (term
111 contractions, preterm contractions, preterm PRM followed by contractions and
112 hourglass membranes (HM)) and the GA at which this event started, the via of
113 delivery (vaginal, assisted vaginal, cesarean due to dystocia and cesarean
114 due to abnormal CTG), birth weight (BW), birth weight centile, fetal sex, Apgar
115 score at 5 minutes, arterial pH, and baby destiny (maternal ward, neonates
116 ward and intensive care pediatric unit).

117 PTB was defined as any spontaneous onset of labor prior to 37 weeks [26]. In
118 some cases, patients debuted initially with uterine contractions and
119 subsequent cervical shortening. In others, they debuted with preterm rupture
120 of membranes (PRM) and subsequent contractions. Finally, a few cases
121 started as hourglass membranes (HM) delivering at very early GA
122 representing the PTB subgroup with the highest severity. PRM was defined as
123 the rupture of amniotic membranes prior to 37 weeks, while HM was defined
124 by the presence of bulging membranes through the cervical external os at the
125 speculum examination, usually with slight spotting and absent or minor uterine
126 contractions. In all cases and to ascertain the diagnosis, HM were also
127 visualized with transvaginal ultrasound. All HM cases either delivered
128 spontaneously without obstetrical intervention or finished in late-term
129 miscarriage (<24 weeks).

130 As per local protocol, and in line with international guidelines, prior to 34+6
131 weeks, cases of PTB starting with uterine contractions were treated with
132 intravenous atosiban (Tractocile®) plus betamethasone (Celestone®) to
133 achieve lung maturation [26,27]. In addition, cases with PRM were treated
134 with triple antibiotic therapy (ampicillin 1g/6 hours, gentamicin 80 mg/8 hours
135 and azitromicin 1g single dose), lung maturation and induction over 34 weeks.

136 Finally, prior to 32 weeks intravenous magnesium sulphate was also
137 administered as neuroprotectant in order to diminish the possibility of brain
138 damage and neurological sequelae.

139 In order to study the possible relationships with PTB, all pregnancy
140 characteristics were analyzed, describing their means, standard deviations
141 (SD), medians and interquartile ranges (IQR) (25%-75%). Subsequently, the
142 existence of differences between TB and PTB groups was assessed by mean
143 of univariable analysis. In addition, correlations of FHR and NT with GA at
144 birth were performed and severity trends were investigated. Finally,
145 multivariable logistic regression analysis were calculated to confirm the
146 associations between these parameters and PTB prior to 37, 34, 32 and 28
147 weeks and HM, describing the Odds ratios (OR), OR 95% confidence
148 intervals (OR 95% CI) and P-values.

149 Comparisons were made with Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous data and
150 Fisher's exact tests for frequency data. Severity trends for NT and FHR were
151 evaluated by mean of Kruskal-Wallis tests and correlation was done using
152 Pearson Coefficient R^2 . Statistical analysis and graphs were done with
153 StatPlus® for Mac, version 7 and GraphPad Prism® for Mac, version 5.
154 Significance was established at a P-value below 0.05.

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170 **RESULTS**

171 The characteristics of the study population are shown in table 1. In summary,
172 it included 518 fetuses, of which most (51.1%) were of male sex and delivered
173 at term (52.5%). The mean maternal age, gravidity, parity and BMI were 32.3,
174 2.1, 0.6 and 24.1, and the mean GA at examination, labor onset and delivery
175 12.4, 36.9 and 37.1 weeks. All pregnancies initiated labor spontaneously,
176 delivering mostly vaginally (73.5%). In most cases, neonates were born
177 uneventfully and accompanied the mother to the maternity ward (79.5%).
178 Moreover, only 1.3 % had an Apgar score below 7 at 5 minutes, while 3.9%
179 had neonatal cord pHs below 7.10. Although 55.8% needed admission to
180 postnatal pediatric care, the proportion of fetuses below the 10th centile was
181 close to the general population (14.1%).

182 Table 2 compares PTB and TB characteristics. In summary, PTB fetuses
183 (N=246) presented higher NT ($p<0.0001$) and FHR ($p=0.0017$) values and a
184 higher frequency of smoking ($p=0.0256$) Apgar score below 7 at 5 minutes
185 ($p<0.0001$), scheduled cesarean section ($p=0.0111$), smallness for gestational
186 age ($p=0.0225$), pediatric admission ($p<0.0001$) and male sex ($p<0.0001$).

187 Figure 1 compares FHR and NT values between TB and PTB fetuses
188 delivering at different GA (<37, <34, <32, <28 and HM). FHR and NT
189 differences were significant at all GA ($P<0.05$ to $P<0.0001$). In addition a
190 severity trend was observed for both parameters ($P<0.001$, $P<0.0001$), with
191 higher FHR and NT values in the most severe cases of PTB (HM). Moreover,
192 both, FHR and NT, correlated with GA at PTB ($R^2=0.016$, $P<0.05$ and
193 $R^2=0.042$, $P<0.0001$).

194 Finally, table 3 describes the multivariable logistic regression analysis
195 studying the associations of several parameters, with PTB at different GA.
196 Both parameters, NT and FHR, were selected as independent determinants of
197 PTB ($P<0.0001$ to $P<0.05$ and $P<0.01$ to $P<0.05$ depending on GA) and
198 maintained this condition at all degrees of PTB severity.

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204 **DISCUSSION**

205 Summary of findings

206 This study shows that first trimester NT and FHR associate with late, early
207 and very early PTB, and that this association shows for both parameters a
208 severity trend.

209 Comparison with existing literature

210 This is the first study to describe the association of FHR and NT with PTB.

211 Our data agree with previous reports suggesting that high NT values
212 associate with different adverse outcomes, including PTB [25, 28]. However in
213 these works information provided by FHR was not included. They are also in
214 line with previous reports showing the association of PTB with several
215 maternal and fetal characteristics, like body mass index [29], smoking [30],
216 male sex [31] and assisted reproduction [32].

217 We did not found a clear physiopathological explanation for the association of
218 TN and FHR with PTB, apart from the general association of NT with adverse
219 outcome [25]. However, as PTB has been frequently related with inflammation
220 [6-8], we hypothesized the possibility to link this condition with those changes
221 observed in FHR, in analogy to those seen in type I diabetes, a chronic
222 process, which interestingly has also been related with both PTB and fetal and
223 mother FHR variations [12,13,23,33-38].

224 Several relationships support a plausible role of inflammation on FHR: First,
225 chronic diseases and maternal poor health cause inflammation, increasing the
226 incidence PTB [39,40]. Second, preterm and term labor have been related
227 with an increase of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the fetal [41,42] and
228 maternal [43] compartments. And third, cytokines produced during
229 inflammation have been associated with heart rate changes, including
230 tachycardia and changes of variability [18-22]. Consequently, it would be
231 possible to expect relationships between FHR, cytokines and PTB. In addition,
232 we have suggested a correlation between ultrasound changes, and severity of
233 PTB, which might suggest a role for the intensity of inflammation in the
234 promptness of PTB.

235 Clinical implications

236 Prediction of PTB is currently based on cervical length measurement at 20
237 weeks [44]. However, cost-effectiveness studies are still controversial and the

238 efficacy and implementation protocol is under debate [45,46]. This work
239 suggests the theoretical possibility to screen for PTB earlier in pregnancy,
240 using data collected in the entire fetal population during the 12 weeks scan.
241 The information obtained might be used to stratify risks and define the access
242 to PTB prediction at 20 weeks using cervical length.

243 Strengths and weaknesses

244 The strengths are the accurate statistical methodology, and especially its
245 novelty, as there are no previous studies evaluating the association of PTB in
246 the first trimester with simple data available at the 12 weeks ultrasound. Of
247 note, NT and FHR kept their importance throughout all GA proving that
248 whatever might be the mechanism triggering PTB, both cardiovascular
249 parameters are called to play a role as PTB markers. Shortcomings include
250 the retrospective nature of the study and the different importance of the
251 different maternal parameters, which might be due to the moderate number of
252 cases included.

253 Conclusion

254 Fetuses developing PTB show higher values of NT and FHR at the first
255 trimester scan. Future studies are needed to validate these results and
256 evaluate these parameters as possible markers of PTB.

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272 **Acknowledgement**

273 To the midwife team and the auxiliary personnel at the labor ward for their
274 assistance in collecting delivery data.

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276 **Statement of ethics**

277 Being a retrospective study in which all data were collected during the routine
278 clinical management there was not a need to obtain informed consents.
279 However an IRB authorization was obtained for the study (Reference
280 2014/0063).

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282 **Conflict of interest statement:**

283 The authors report no conflict of interests.

284

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290 **Author Contributions:**

291 José Morales-Roselló did the study design, collected cases, performed the
292 statistical analysis and wrote the manuscript.

293

294 Gabriela Loscalzo, Gemma Perez, Alicia Soriano and Vaidilė Jakaitė collected
295 cases and participated actively in the review of the manuscript.

296

297 Alfredo Perales Marín

298 Contributed to the study design and participated actively in the review of the
299 manuscript.

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475 **FIGURES**

476

477 **Figure 1.** (Upper left) First trimester FHR values in TB and PTB fetuses
478 delivering prior to 37, 34, 32, 28 weeks. (Upper right) First trimester NT values
479 obtained in TB and PTB fetuses delivering prior to 37, 34, 32, 28 weeks. In
480 both cases HM was added as the group with highest severity and earliest
481 PTB. (Lower left) Correlation between FHR and GA at birth. (Lower right)
482 Correlation between NT and GA at birth.

483